

CURRENT ISSUES IN SUMMARIZING, ANALYZING, AND REPORTING ON PRE-INVESTIGATION INSPECTION RESULTS IN INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

Eraliyev Asrorjon Rustamovich

Chief Inspector of the Department for Handling Appeals,
Organizational Department, Ministry of Internal Affairs of the
Republic of Uzbekistan, Lieutenant Colonel
Independent Researcher at the Academy
of the Ministry of Internal Affairs

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Abstract. The article highlights the significance of registering and reviewing applications, reports, and other information about crimes, summarizing the results of pre-investigation checks, analyzing them, and maintaining reports, developing effective methods for combating crime based on the analysis of pre-investigation checks, and their main role in identifying crimes and taking legal measures against them.

Keywords: internal affairs bodies, investigator, inquiry officer, official of the pre-investigation check body, application for a crime, pre-investigation check, analysis and report.

A necessary condition for building a state governed by the rule of law and a civil society is the unconditional observance of laws. The uniform and unconditional implementation of laws depends on the attitude of our lawyers to their duties and a sense of responsibility[1].

The pre-investigation investigation, which is the subject of the study, includes measures to verify criminal applications, reports and other information, to make a decision based on the results of their consideration, as well as measures to secure and preserve traces of crime, objects and documents that may be relevant to the case[2].

Pre-investigation investigation is the initial stage of the criminal process, which includes the verification of criminal applications, reports and other information and the issue of initiating or refusing to initiate a criminal case.

This stage is also the initial stage of the process of protecting the legitimate interests of citizens who have suffered as a result of criminal acts. Pre-investigation investigation is the legal basis for conducting investigative actions aimed at determining the presence or absence of a criminal act on the basis of the collected materials. It initially appeared as a criminal procedural institution, constituting a set of procedural norms determining the procedure for resolving the issue of initiating a criminal case[3].

The consideration and resolution of criminal complaints and reports is carried out in compliance with the requirements established by the criminal procedural legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Previously, the conduct of pre-investigation checks was regulated by the internal regulatory legal acts of each pre-investigation body. In particular, the unified procedure for receiving, registering, and keeping records of applications, reports, and other information on crimes and incidents requiring pre-investigation investigation in the prosecutor's offices of the Republic of Uzbekistan, registering and keeping records of decisions made on resolved cases, and monitoring these processes is established by the order of the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan[4]. In the internal affairs bodies, which are more involved in pre-investigation investigation activities than other bodies, the procedure for receiving, registering, considering, and keeping records of applications, reports, and other information on crimes and incidents, strengthening centralized accounting,

accounting discipline, and ensuring full compliance with the requirements of current legislation in making legal decisions is carried out in accordance with the Instruction approved by the order of the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan[5].

The main tasks of the internal affairs bodies are to protect the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens, the property of individuals and legal entities, the constitutional order, ensuring the rule of law, the security of the individual, society and the state, as well as the prevention and prevention of crimes. The law obliges the internal affairs bodies to keep records of crimes and administrative offenses, persons who committed them, victims of offenses, those declared wanted, missing persons, and those in possession of civil and service weapons, to plan and implement preventive measures, to analyze this data and to implement preventive measures[6].

The instruction, approved by the order of the Minister of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 12, 2016 No. 180 "On approval of the Instruction on the procedure for receiving, registering, considering and accounting of applications, reports and other information on crimes and incidents in internal affairs bodies", establishes that the purpose of keeping records of applications is to reflect in statistical reports information and indicators on the number of applications received and registered by internal affairs bodies on crimes and incidents, the level of social danger, their type, consideration within the established deadlines, measures taken, procedural decisions made based on the results of the investigation. According to it, information on crimes and incidents received by the duty unit of the internal affairs body is immediately registered in the Form 1 book or Form 2 journal, and the head of the relevant body is informed about this. The consideration of applications and reports is organized in accordance with the requirements of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Instruction.

The Instruction stipulates that the semi-annual and annual statistical report on the results of the consideration of applications and reports on crimes and incidents by the accounting officer of the internal affairs body shall be compiled in accordance with Appendix 6 to the Instruction, the form 1 book and the form 2 journal shall be considered as the basis for compiling the report, the accounting officer shall keep records of materials on the refusal to initiate a criminal case based on the results of the consideration of registered applications, the accounting officer shall compare the information in the journal with the form 1 book and the form 2 journal in the duty unit at the end of each month and draw up an act based on the results of the comparison.

As part of the judicial and legal reforms, from December 1, 2018, the Information Center of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its territorial divisions were liquidated, and 258 staff units were allocated to the newly established Department of Criminal Law Statistics within the General Prosecutor's Office, as well as its criminal law statistics departments within the structures of the prosecutor's offices of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and Tashkent city. As a result, the staff units of the accounting officer in the internal affairs bodies were completely liquidated and transferred to the General Prosecutor's Office.

About two and a half years later, the Department of Criminal Law Statistics and territorial divisions of the General Prosecutor's Office were liquidated, and 120 staff units of the General Prosecutor's Office were returned to the Ministry of Internal Affairs[7].

Also, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 10, 2020, stipulates that the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan, together with interested ministries and departments, shall ensure that the software module, which allows for electronic registration of criminal applications, reports and other information created in the unified information system "Electronic Criminal and Legal Statistics" and maintaining a single electronic record of the results of their consideration, is connected to all bodies conducting pre-investigation inspections and is fully operational from January 1, 2021, and that a draft regulatory legal document establishing the procedure for receiving and considering applications, reports and other information about crimes, as well as conducting pre-investigation inspection actions, is developed within three months[8].

In accordance with the Presidential Decree, this decision was canceled by a joint decision of the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the State Security Service, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Ministry of Emergency Situations, the Ministry of Defense, the State Customs Committee and the National Guard, and a joint decision was adopted on the procedure for receiving, registering and considering applications, reports and other information on crimes and incidents, as well as exercising control over the pre-investigation verification process, as well as establishing the procedure for operating the "E-material" system, in accordance with the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and legislative acts[9].

The joint decision stipulated that the simultaneous use of paper forms for registering applications, reports and other information on crimes and incidents and the "E-material" electronic system is allowed until July 1, 2021, and from July 1, 2021, registration will be carried out only through the

"E-material" electronic system.

This opened up a wide range of opportunities for collecting information on the receipt, registration and resolution of criminal complaints, analyzing them and making management decisions.

As is known, the information-analytical activities of the internal affairs bodies are regulated by a separate ministerial order, which include:

collection, generalization and analysis of information received from internal affairs and state administration bodies, public organizations and other sources on socio-political, economic, demographic, interethnic and other processes affecting the criminogenic situation in the service area;

comprehensive analysis of problems in the fight against crime, prevention of offenses, and law enforcement activities;

conducting social and criminological research to identify processes that threaten public security and study the conditions and factors that cause them, and determining the prospects for the development of threats;

to develop information and analytical documents to assess the results of the activities of the internal affairs body, stabilize the operational situation in the service area and increase the efficiency of the activities of sectoral services;

to prepare analytical data, report abstracts and reports for the head of the internal affairs body;

to form a data and information fund in the internal affairs body[10].

Information and analytical activities related to the reception, registration, consideration and accounting of applications, reports and other information on crimes and incidents in internal affairs bodies, centralized accounting, strengthening accounting discipline play an important role in identifying problems and taking effective measures to address them. The main importance of this process is clearly manifested in the tasks of collecting and analyzing information, developing effective measures to combat crime, developing legal and preventive measures, and increasing the effectiveness of informed decision-making.

During the collection and analysis of information, after receiving applications, reports and other information on crimes and incidents, final decisions are compiled based on the results of the pre-investigation investigation. This information helps to identify in which regions there is an increase in applications about crimes. For example, in 2024, a total of 289,758 criminal complaints were investigated by preventive inspectors of internal affairs bodies, 41,230 of which were considered by the Tashkent City Internal Affairs Department and its subordinate systems[11]. This analytical data serves as the basis for analyzing criminal complaints and taking measures to increase the effectiveness of combating them.

The task of developing effective measures to combat crime is to monitor the dynamics of crimes and incidents, reports and other information, and the results of pre-investigation investigations, which help to monitor the dynamics of crimes and develop effective preventive measures against them. For example, in 2024, a total of 289,578 criminal complaints were investigated by preventive inspectors, and a decision was made to refuse to initiate criminal proceedings in 223,770 of them[12]. This will help increase understanding of the reasons for the receipt of criminal reports and strengthen preventive measures.

The development of legal and preventive measures, on the basis of the collected data, allows us to identify the social, economic and moral causes of crime. Most crimes are associated with difficult social and economic conditions. Analysis of criminal complaints serves as the basis for preventing crimes and developing preventive measures against them.

The task of increasing the effectiveness of decision-making is to make decisions on each application based on complaints, reports and other information about crimes and incidents, as well as on the results of pre-investigation investigations. The accuracy of the data and their analysis help to choose an effective direction for making informed decisions in the fight against crime. The information obtained through complaints and pre-investigation investigations helps to identify the causes of these complaints and eliminate their consequences.

Because increasing the effectiveness of work on combating crime and preventing offenses, ensuring preventive registration of persons who have committed crimes, as well as preventing crimes from being hidden from registration, is one of the urgent tasks of law enforcement agencies[13].

In conclusion, it can be said that the information analysis activity related to the generalization, analysis and reporting of the results of pre-investigation inspections of internal affairs bodies serves to ensure the development of timely, justified and effective management decisions by the head of the internal affairs body in maintaining law and order and combating crime, as well as in the implementation of other tasks of the internal affairs body.

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